

A Study on Brand Impact of Apparels on Consumer Buying Behaviour in Kukatpally Area

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How to cite this paper: Dr. R. Narsaiah | R Shashi Preetham "A Study on Brand Impact of Apparels on Consumer Buying Behaviour in Kukatpally Area" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-3, April 2019, pp.514-517, URL: <http://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd22838.pdf>

IJTSRD22838

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ABSTRACT

The paper is about the results of the primary research which purpose was to know the impact of apparels brand on consumers to purchase a product. The aim of the paper is to make the fact clear that the brand has an impact on customer decision-making process. The Primary data has been collected from 128 respondents within the region of Kukatpally area. Questionnaire is framed containing 20 questions which were asked to consumers in Kukatpally area. The secondary data has been collected from internet, books, references etc. Though the different media spread awareness but television advertising plays a vital role in buying behaviour of consumers. The outcome generated from descriptive statistics is that most of the respondents has positive opinion on television advertisements. From the findings, we can also see that there is no significant association between gender of respondents and buying behaviour towards branded apparels. There is a significant association between income of the respondents and frequency of buying branded apparels. There is no difference between male and female groups with respect to the awareness of television advertisements.

KEYWORDS: Buying behaviour, Branded apparels

1. INTRODUCTION

The purchasing process is a combination of mental and physical activities that ends with an actual purchase. Therefore it is interesting to study the connection with in what and why we buy it. In this circumstance, brands play a main role in consumer decision making. There are many factors of consumers effecting their opinions and decisions. In today's increasing competitive marketplace, Consumers differ in their perceptions; they would necessarily hold different images for any specific apparel brand and often have to make a choice among a range of apparel brands in the market that differ very little in its price. In such circumstances, their final decision depends on the image they have with different brands. All the study has been conducted with reference to apparels industry. Firms in apparels industry are competing to increase their profit share in the market and among these firms; branded clothing has shifted the conventional style and interest of people. A brand is sold at a high price and the other is sold at low price while both have same quality and attributes, why is that? Brand studies always remained the key attention of the marketers because of its importance and direct relationship with consumers. Marketers use brands as to get the competitive advantage on other competitors playing an imperative role in the success of companies. Brand holds a great importance in consumer's life. Consumer's choose brands and trust them the way they trust their friends and

family members to avoid uncertainty and quality related issues. India has a successful growing economy and the clothing industry of the country has grown tremendously in the recent years. The increasing use of branded apparels and the emerging market has intrigued foreign as well as local brands to provide services to its customers.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objectives of the study are:

1. To study the demographics of the respondents with their preferences towards attributes of branded apparels
2. To study the frequency of buying branded apparels of the respondents with their income levels.
3. To study the gender preferences with respect to influence of branded apparels on them.
4. To study how respondents get to know about a particular apparel brand.

3. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

According to Aaker (2004), in brand equity consumer only makes purchase to same brand regardless of the demonstrated benefits. Consumer loyalty means a brand has a very strong position in the market and the chances of consumers to switch another brand becomes low and consumers are willing to purchase the same brand, they want to invest money in that particular brand.

According to Keller (2003), the fact that consumers purchase the same brand continuously is not brand loyalty. They just do it because of their common habits that don't change or they are being attracted by purchase offers or any other promotional tool.

According to Driessen (2005), companies can create strong brand image and recognition through advertisement. He explained that by advertisement, companies try to target teenagers and youth. They are attracted towards traditional advertisement more easily than adults those who are mature. They show positive reaction and quick reaction to the company's advertisement. Older person has more purchasing experience than younger one.

4. METHODOLOGY

This study is based on the primary data collected through a sample of 128 people. The questionnaire was constructed to understand the impact of branded apparels on consumer buying behaviour. The data was collected through a survey along with the detailed demographics of the participants. Secondary data was collected from various sources such as books, journals, and online resources. This questionnaire was distributed to 128 people in Kukatpally area. So the final sample size is 128. The questionnaire was sent by e-mail and What's app contacts in the form of Google forms. The completed questionnaire was sent back through email and responses were updated in Google forms. Hyderabad is a place where we can see people with different cultures and customs. Since Hyderabad is technically developed, research is conducted in this area. It is conducted using quantitative as well as qualitative method. Quantitative data is collected with the help of questionnaire. The data collected from the questionnaire is analysed using the mathematical tools and the result is presented in tables for clear understanding to the reader. The conclusions are drawn from the findings. The collected data are logically and systematically entered using SPSS software and analysis done as per the requirement of study. Descriptive analysis is done for analysing the data. Central tendency, frequency table, Chart, Graph and Chi-square are used for descriptive analysis. Whereas Hypothesis testing, Chi-square test, t-test are done for internal analysis.

5. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

1. Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant association between age and attributes while selecting branded apparel.
Alternative Hypothesis (H1): There is a significant association between age and attributes while selecting branded apparel.
2. Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant association between income of the respondents and frequency of buying branded apparels.
Alternative Hypothesis (H1): There is a significant association between earnings of the respondents and frequency of buying branded apparels.

3. Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no difference between male and female groups with respect to influence of branded apparels on buying behaviour.
Alternative Hypothesis (H1): There is a difference between male and female groups with respect to influence of branded apparels on buying behaviour.

6. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

6.1 Demographic profile of respondents

Age
128 responses

Figure 1: Age analysis

Gender
128 responses

Figure 2: Gender analysis

a. Descriptive statistics:

128 responses

Figure 3: Frequency of buying

128 responses

Figure 4: Attributes of respondents while choosing a branded apparel

6.2 Cross tabulation analysis

6.2.1 Cross tabulation of age and attributes while selecting a branded apparel

Attributes while selecting a branded apparel	Age				Total
	15- 20	20- 25	25- 30	Above 30	
Quality	16	77	4	7	104
Cost	12	58	3	3	76
Durability	6	59	4	3	72
Availability	6	36	1	3	46
Total	18	97	6	7	128

Table 1: Cross Tabulation of age and attributes While selecting a branded apparel

6.2.2 Cross tabulation of income of respondents and frequency of their buying branded apparels

Income level	Frequency of buying				Total
	Monthly	Occasionally	Weekly	Yearly	
Less than 15000	2	19	0	1	22
15000 - 20000	0	7	0	0	7
20000 - 50000	4	12	2	0	18
Greater than 50000	8	8	0	0	16
No income	10	49	4	2	65
Total	24	95	6	3	128

Table 2: Cross tabulation of income of respondents and frequency of their buying branded apparels

b. Chi square analysis

6.3.1 Analysis of age and attributes while selecting branded apparels

Here, the analysis covers all the statistical analysis made to verify the hypothesis and ascertain the significance of age and attributes while selecting branded apparels.

Pearson Chi-Square Tests		
Attributes while selecting branded apparels	Chi-square	11.445
	df	12
	Sig.	0.491

Table 3: Analysis of age and attributes while selecting branded apparel

We can see that as the chi- square value (0.491) is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore we accept the null hypothesis and we can conclude that there is no significant association between age and attributes while selecting branded apparel.

6.3.2 Analysis of income of respondents and frequency of their buying branded apparels

Here, the analysis covers all the statistical analysis made to verify the hypothesis and ascertain the significance of income of respondents and frequency of their buying branded apparels

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	19.285	20	0.046
Likelihood Ratio	20.808	20	0.049
N of Valid Cases	128		

Table 4: Analysis of income of respondents and frequency of their buying branded apparels

We can see that as the chi- square value (0.046) is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept alternate hypothesis. Hence, we can conclude that there is a significant association between income of respondents and frequency of their buying branded apparels.

6.4 Independent t- test

6.4.1 Analysis of the gender and influence of apparels brand on buying behaviour

Here, the analysis covers all the statistical analysis made to verify the hypothesis and ascertain the significance of gender and influence of apparels brand on buying behaviour.

Group statistics

	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Influence of apparels brand on buying behavior	Male	79	1.608	0.4914	0.0553
	Female	49	1.673	0.4738	0.0677

Table 5: Group statistics

Independent samples test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means				
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2 tailed)	Mean difference	Std. error difference
Influence of apparels brand on buying behaviour	Equal variances assumed	2.409	0.123	- 747	126	0.456	-.0659	0.0882
	Equal variances not assumed			- 754	104.729	0.453	-.0659	0.0874

Table 6: Independent samples test

As we can see from the Table 6, the p- value is 0.456 which is greater than 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted and we can conclude that there is no difference among male and female groups with respect to influence of branded apparels on them.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study there are some research limitations with regard to the convenience sampling as the number of respondents is restricted to only Kukatpally. Hence, it may not be a perfect representation of the population. Furthermore, there is a chance of response errors due to many factors such as misinterpretation, hesitation, unawareness and so on among the respondents. The study shows that apparels brand has an influence on buying behaviour of the consumers. The paper also concludes that independent of age, attributes preferred by consumers are same. It also concludes that income of consumers affect frequency of their buying branded apparels. From this paper, we can also see that independent of gender, both male and female groups are influenced by brand of apparels. From this paper, it was found that advertisements play a major role in making consumers know about a branded apparel. It was also concluded that consumers feel more comfortable and satisfied in purchasing the branded apparels they already experienced.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bengtsson, A. (2002). Consumer and mixed brands- on the polysemy of brand meaning, KFS AB Lund.
- [2] Bernard, H. R. (2011). Research methods in anthropology: Qualitative and quantitative approaches: Altamira press.
- [3] Aaker, J.L., "Dimensions of brand personality", Journal of Marketing Research, vol. 34, pp. 347-56, 1997.
- [4] Keller, K., 'Conceptualizing, measuring, and managing customer-based brand equity', Journal of Marketing, vol. 57, pp. 1-22, 1993.
- [5] Gajjar., "Factor affecting consumer behavior", vol. 1, no. 2, April, 2013.
- [6] Moor-Shay, E. S., 'Intergenerational influences in the formation of consumer attitudes and beliefs about marketplace: Mothers and Daughters', Advances in Consumer Research, vol. 15, pp. 461-467, 1988.
- [7] Kilsheimer, J., 'Status Consumption: The Development and Implications of a Scale Measuring the Motivation to Consume for Status', a dissertation submitted to the Marketing Faculty at Florida State University, FL, 1993.
- [8] Shermach, K., 'What consumers wish brand managers knew', Marketing News, vol. 31, no. 12, 9th June, 1997.
- [9] Beri G.C. (2008) 'Marketing Research' 4th Edition Tata Mc-Graw Hill company